

Questionnaire

Section 1 - Demographics

Prompt	Possible Answers
(1) What is/are your college majors?	<i>Free-form text</i>
(2) What is your educational level? <i>If you are currently working towards a degree, and this degree is higher than previous degrees, please choose the level of the degree you are currently working towards.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>BS/BA</i>• <i>MS/MA</i>• <i>PhD</i>
(3) How many years have passed since you graduated from your highest degree?	<i>Number entry</i>
(4) How many years of experience do you have in the aerospace domain? <i>Besides work experience, please also count school projects and classes if they are in the aerospace domain.</i>	<i>Number entry</i>
(5) Do you think of yourself as a software developer?	<i>Yes/No</i>

Section 2 – Exercise 1

In this exercise you will be asked to model and search for a simple geometric event with the two different language options. You will see an example with both languages. You will use the example as a starting point to model the new event.

Example in Language A	Example in Language B
<pre>DEF event1 AS DISTANCE FROM Moon TO Earth LESS THAN 40K DURING 01/01/2000:12/31/2005</pre>	<pre>DistanceQuery event1{ observer: "Moon" target: "Earth" test: < amount: 40K start_time: 01/01/2000 end_time: 12/31/2005 }</pre>

Event: "Earth and Mars are at a distance of more than 70M km in all of 2021".

Prompt	Possible Good Answers
Please model the event above with Language A	<p><i>Free-form text.</i> One possible good answer:</p> <pre>DEF event_name AS DISTANCE FROM Earth TO Mars MORE THAN 70M DURING 01/01/2021:12/31/2021 SEARCH FOR event2</pre>
Please model the event above with Language B	<p><i>Free-form text.</i> One possible good answer:</p> <pre>DistanceQuery event2{ observer: "Earth" target: "Mars" test: > amount: 70M start_time: 01/01/2021 end_time: 12/31/2021 } SEARCH FOR event2</pre>

Section 3 – Exercise 2

In this exercise you will be asked to model a composite geometric event with the two different language options. You will see a new type of event and its definition in both languages. You will use that as a starting point to model the new event.

Occultation Events in Language A	Occultation Events in Language B
<pre>OccultationEvent event1{ type: {"any", "full", "annular", "partial"} back_body: "backBody" front_body: "frontBody" observer: "observerBody" start_time: startTime end_time: endTime } SEARCH FOR event1</pre>	<pre>DEF event1 AS {ANY, FULL, ANNULAR, PARTIAL} OCCULTATION BETWEEN BACK BODY body1 AND FRONT BODY body2 OBSERVED BY BODY observer DURING startTime:endTime SEARCH FOR event1</pre>

Event: "Earth and Mars are at a distance of more than 70M km, and at the same time, Mars and Earth are in full solar conjunction (solar conjunction is when the Sun is between two bodies). Use the 2010-2020 interval".

Prompt	Possible Good Answers
Please model the event above with Language A	<p><i>Free-form text.</i> One possible good answer:</p> <pre>DistanceQuery event1{ observer: "Earth" target: "Mars" test: > amount: 70M start_time: 01/01/2010 end_time: 12/31/2020 } OccultationEvent event2{ type: "full" back_body: "Mars" front_body: "Sun" observer: "Earth" start_time: 01/01/2010 end_time: 12/31/2020 } SEARCH FOR event1 AND event2</pre>
Please model the event above with Language B	<p><i>Free-form text.</i> One possible good answer:</p> <pre>DEF event1 AS FULL OCCULTATION BETWEEN BACK BODY Mars AND FRONT BODY Sun OBSERVED BY BODY Earth DURING 01/01/2010:12/31/2020 DEF event2 AS DISTANCE FROM Moon TO Earth MORE THAN 70M DURING 01/01/2010:12/31/2020 SEARCH FOR event1 AND event2</pre>

Sections 4-14 – Usability Questions

Author's note: These sections included an example in each language option, and below each example, the statements below. Respondents selected a response on a Likert 1-5 scale for each question and for each language option. In this Likert 1-5 scale, 1 indicated "Strongly Disagree" and 5 indicated "Strongly Agree". Section 4 was a question on readability, whereas Sections 5-14 were part of the System Usability Scale (SUS).

- Section 4: I think the language above is readable by a scientist or engineer
- Section 5: *I think that I would like to use the language above frequently*
- Section 6: *I found the language above unnecessarily complex*
- Section 7: *I thought the language above was easy to use*
- Section 8: *I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use the language above*
- Section 9: *I found the various functions in the language above were well integrated*
- Section 10: *I thought there was too much inconsistency in the language above*
- Section 11: *I would imagine that most people would learn to use the language above very quickly*
- Section 12: *I found the language above very cumbersome (awkward) to use*
- Section 13: *I felt very confident using the language above*
- Section 14: *I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the language above*